

CONCEPTS OF CULTURE AND ETHICS OF VEHICLE DRIVER

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Abstract: *The professional culture of drivers includes legal and moral culture, ideas about the social significance of a certain type of work. In science, the concepts of culture, professional culture and professional culture of drivers are used. The article examines and reveals the concept of culture and ethical standards of vehicle drivers.*

Key words: *culture, ethics, driver ethics, driver's professional culture, driving culture, moral relations between traffic participants.*

Introduction

The term “driver culture” refers to relations on public roads, which generally characterize the level of relationships and mutual benefit of all road users. It is understood that the driver behind the wheel follows the traffic rules, does not create emergency situations, and generally tries not to cause inconvenience to both other vehicle drivers and pedestrians.

There is a fairly large set of rules, which are called driving culture. Even a new driver is capable of following these unspoken instructions. What's included:

Compliance with traffic rules is the first sign of respect for other drivers. And even if one of them himself performed a strange maneuver, there is no need to be nervous and swear. It is better to try to understand what this driver will do next in order to prevent an emergency in advance [1].

If you see a broken-down vehicle on the side of the road, stop and offer help. Perhaps it is not needed or you are unable to help. But in any case, showing sympathy and paying attention to the problems of others is a sign of good manners.

When parking, position your car so that it does not take up unnecessary space. And especially don't park your car closer to a parked car. However, it happens that

there are no other options left: then be sure to leave your phone number on a piece of paper under the glass.

If a car standing at a traffic light does not move too quickly, do not honk persistently at this driver. After all, you can just blink your headlights - and he will understand everything without negative emotions.

When a neighboring car has problems, inform the car owner about it.

When approaching a red traffic light or traffic jam, give way to cars turning left. Personally, this will practically not delay you; you will still have to stand! But by blocking the path, you are depriving your neighbors of at least a few minutes. The same goes for pedestrians at a traffic-congested intersection: let people pass rather than stand right at the crossing.

Of course, the driving culture in the post-Soviet space is not yet at the level it should be at. However, she is partially helped by unspoken ethical standards developed over many years of driving practice dating back to the times of the Soviet Union. [2].

In science, the concepts of culture, professional culture and professional culture of drivers are used. Culture means the material and spiritual values created by humanity.

Professional culture is a high level of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the successful implementation of a certain type of activity. The professional culture of drivers is integral part of universal human culture. Based on this, drivers in their activities comply with the requirements of universal human culture and professional driver culture. By professional driver culture we mean that the person performing the service performs his duties at a high level from the point of view of law, morality and justice [3].

The professional culture of drivers includes legal and moral culture, ideas about the social significance of a certain type of work. The main aspect of the professional culture of drivers is that it is normative in nature, that is, the requirements for the cultural image of drivers are determined by regulatory documents. The professional culture of drivers is reflected in their treatment of citizens, the protection of the rights, interests of citizens, legislation, public order based on current laws, ethical and legal norms and clothing.

In ensuring road safety, people are the main participants of the road and take part as drivers, passengers, and pedestrians. Among them, the most important place is occupied by the driver. Therefore, when organizing traffic, it is necessary to take into account the psychological, physiological and biological capabilities of the driver.

Driver ethics are standards of behavior, morality, and a set of moral rules for the driver. It is a philosophical science that studies moral issues, is considered one of the most important aspects of human life, and teaches a person the right way of life based on his own character. That is why ethics includes the theory of human life, the study of emotions and at the same time teaching ways to achieve a prosperous life and happiness [4].

The driver's ethics are manifested in his discipline, sense of responsibility, and such moral qualities as his attitude towards the team. Hard work, kindness to people, modesty are qualities characteristic of good and reliable people. Lack of interest in work, arrogance, rudeness, disrespect for others, disrespect for order and discipline, exhibits the qualities of a person prone to causing accidents.

Driver indiscipline usually manifests itself in non-compliance with traffic rules on the roads. The driver must think not only about his own safety, but also about the safety of other road users. He only observes the behavior of others without strictly observing the rules [5].

Discussion

A real driver is polite and attentive - he will not twist his finger at his temple and, opening the window, shout curses at an unwary pedestrian. A person endowed with such traits as aggressiveness, instability, hostility, impoliteness, arrogance, disdain for the opinions of others and the inability to think about the consequences of his words and actions cannot be considered a good, reliable driver.

Any of these unacceptable qualities can lead to disaster under certain circumstances. For example, under the influence of aggressiveness, a driver commits many dangerous actions: he is easily "infected" by the increased speed of an overtaking car, trying to get around the "offender" at any cost [6].

Conclusion

And when it is necessary to give way to a traffic participant who has an advantage, contrary to common sense, he tries to get past. When he gets into the same lane with a vehicle that, in his opinion, is not moving fast enough, he gets angry and overtakes, even if overtaking is prohibited. Seeing a vehicle approaching an intersection that could interfere with him, he does not slow down, but on the contrary, increases speed.

Uncompromising, rude behavior of traffic participants is dangerous for everyone. On the contrary, a friendly and helpful attitude towards each other creates a

favorable, calm environment on the road. Without respectful and polite attitude of all road users towards each other, road safety is impossible.

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